

THE REVIEW OF AXIAL FLUX PERMANENT MAGNET GENERATOR

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ABSTRACT

An Axial Flux Permanent Magnet generator (AFPM) becomes cost effective and attractive alternative to the radial flux permanent magnet generators, specially for low speed and high torque wind applications. This paper investigates and discuss about the different topologies of AFPM generator. The investigation is based upon their stator and rotor construction, their locations in generator, their sizes, and their material etc. The comparison of different topologies of AFPM generator is done in this paper. This paper also discusses basics of their manufacturing process. In last section simple design procedure of AFPM generator is discussed.

KEYWORDS- AFPM generator, single sided, double sided, stator discs, rotor discs.